

WAYS OF PRODUCTIVE WORD FORMATION OF MASS MEDIA TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

O'ktamova Nilufar Nozimjon qizi

Teacher, University of Tashkent for Applied sciences

n.yusupova1994@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article provides the ways of productive word formation of mass media terms in the English and Uzbek languages, as well as the examples of effective ways of constructing mass media terms have been analyzed in both languages.

Key words: word formation, borrowing, compounding, morphological derivation, affixation, acronymy, blending.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tili ommaviy axborot vositalari terminlari yasashidagi sermahsul usullari keltirilgan bo'lib, shuningdek, mazkur tadqiqot davomida ommaviy axborot terminlarining sermahsul usullari yasashiga oid misollar har ikki tilda ham tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z yasalishi, o'zlashma so'zlar, qo'shma so'zlar, morfologik derivatsiya, affiksatsiya, akronimiya, blending.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены способы продуктивного образования терминов СМИ на английском и узбекском языках, а также проанализированы примеры эффективных способов построения терминов СМИ на обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: словообразование, заимствование слова, сложные слова, морфологическая деривация, аффиксация, акронимия, блендинг.

Word formation is nowadays perceived to be such a confused area of study that it would not be possible to write an uncontroversial introduction to the subject. Bauer [Bauer,1986: p.116] recognizes that much of the confusion in word formation studies is terminological.

Borrowing is one of the most important and active productive methods, which enriches the vocabulary of the language. According to Bill Bryson [Bryson p. 27], many lexical units and words in English language came through this method -

borrowing. In linguistics, borrowing (also known as lexical borrowing) is the process by which a word from one language is adapted for use in another. Here we can see some examples for borrowings from English mass media terms:

Italian: *gazette, paparazzi, studio, novel*; French: *kiosk, magazine, journal*; Chinese: *Weibo, duoyin, kuaishou*; Indian: *pundit*; Latin: *radio, propaganda, portal, author, video, globalization, genre, channel, communication, media*; Greek: *comedy, autograph, television, program, hypermedia, hyperlink, photography*. Our research work showed that, borrowings of Uzbek mass media terms include Arabic, Persian, Russian, English and other languages. The followings are some borrowing examples of Uzbek language mass media terminology:

Arabian: *aloqa, matbuot, maktub, xabar, axborot, muxbir, mahalliy, ommaviy, tahrir, sahifa, asar, lavha, loyiha, muxlis, muxlisa, tomosha, ijod, tanqid, tanqidiy, ijro, hajviy, notiq, nutq, varaqa, suhbat, ma'ruza, maqola, taqriz, matbaa, muloqot*; Persian-Tadjik: *suxandon, sarlavha, tomoshabin, ijodkor, matbuotshunos, xabarnoma, axborotnoma, tahlilnoma, savodxon, ro'znoma*; Russian: *adresant, adresat, anons, rejissor, ssenarist*; English: *pamflet, intervyu, informatsiya, brifing, glossariy, onlayn, blog, blogger, multimediya, rialiti shov, tok-shov*; Italian: *gazeta, paparatsiya, studiya*; French: *felyeton, korrespondensiya, ocherk, syujet, remarka, janr*; Latin: *retsenziya, reportaj, diskussiya, televizor, publitsistika, radio, pressa redaksiya, reklama*; Greek: *Komediya, televizor, programma, gipermediya, giperlink, fotografiya*. Besides, the above borrowing terms are acquired in the Uzbek language due to certain linguistic phenomena, for example assimilation and others. As the mass media industry develops, so does mass media borrowings.

Compounding is one of the most productive ways of word-formation in English and Uzbek languages, which “consists in the combination of two or more roots to form a new word” [Bauer, 1986: p.112]. Compounding is a very common process in most languages of the world (especially among synthetic languages). In English, for instance, compound words can be written in three different ways:

a. *Open*, with a space between the parts of the compound: *yellow journalism, mass media, prime time, sketch blog, remote control, print media, social media, soup opera, media bias, mass audience, cross media, tele show, video game, textbook, interview, phone bill, guide book*; b. *Hyphenated*, with a hyphen (-) separating the elements of the compound: *well-informed, co-author, internet-media, multi-author, virtual-reality, web-based, talk-show*; c. *Solid*, without a space or hyphen between the component elements of the compound: *newspaper, broadcast, feedback, Wikipedia, photoblog, postcard, wallpaper, billboard, network, outlet, website, teleshop, newsprint, hyperlink, photocopy, scandalmonger, cameraman, anchorman*.

Examples of this rule can also be observed in Uzbek language:

Morphological derivation is also one of the most productive methods in the formation of mass media terms in English and Uzbek languages. The terms are formed by adding suffixes to existing words. This method is also called affixation [Sarimsakov, 2020: p.87]. As we know, suffixes do not make sense on their own, but when added to the base, it changes their meaning. It also adds meaning to words and syntactically connects words.

dis-, inter-, on-, bi-, extra-, multi-, co-, re-: disinformation, internet, interpersonal, intercommunication, interactive, international, co-author, biweekly, extraordinary, multi-author, biannual, rewrite, reprint

-or: editor; -er: writer, reporter, photographer, publisher, recorder, blogger, YouTuber, TikToker, presenter, producer, follower, subscriber, announcer, advertiser; -ist: journalist, columnist; -ism: journalism, sensationalism; -tion: information, publication; -ing: recording, weekly, monthly, daily, annually, yearly

In Uzbek language, suffixation is also one of the most active methods of word-formation. Uzbek mass media terms are created by adding suffixes to Uzbek native words or borrowing words and it is effective method in mass media terminology. Following we can see several examples of this method:

a. Prefixes: *no-: nofaol, nodavlat, norasmiy; dez-: dezinformatsiya;*

b. Suffixes. We have divided suffixes those create Uzbek mass media terms into following groups: suffixes which create nouns: *-vchi, -chi: boshlovchi, tinglovchi, -iyat, -iyot: tahririyat, nashriyot; -lik: yangilik, noshirlik; -noma: xabarnoma, tahlilnoma; -uv: ko'rsatuv, globallashuv; -ma: qo'lyozma, bosma; suffixes which create adjectives*: *-iy, -viy: ommaviy, tanqidiy; -bop: tomoshabinbop, ommabop; -ar: ko'ngilochar; -li: raqamli, obrazli, tovushli;*

Acronymy is the process whereby a new word is formed from the initial letters of the constituent words of a phrase or sentence. Here we can see some examples of mostly used mass media acronyms in English:

GIF - Graphics Interchange Format; YAHOO - Yet Another Hierarchical Officious Oracle; HTML - Hypertext Markup Language; WWW - World Wide Web; FAQ - frequently asked questions; QR - quick response; CD - compact disc; IP - Internet Protocol, BBC - British Broadcasting Corporation;

However, in contrasting English mass media acronyms to Uzbek mass media acronyms we cannot distinguish them according to their pronunciation. They are pronounced as sequences of letters. Here are some examples from Uzbek mass media acronyms:

OAV – ommaviy axborot vositalari; MTRK – milliy tele radio kompaniya; OAK – oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi; TVR – television and radio; TV – televizor; YOTRK – Yoshlar teleradiokompaniyasi; MTV – Milliy tv; MY5 – Mening Yurtim

Blending is the process whereby new words are formed by combining parts of two words, usually the beginning of one word and the end of another. In English language this method is not productive way in word-formation. But creating mass media terms in this method we can consider it as a productive method. we have analyzed several examples for this method from English language: *camera + recorder = camcorder; sports + broadcast = sportscast; television + broadcast = telecast; network + etiquette = netiquette; European + television = Eurovision; wireless + fidelity = wi-fi; communication + satellite = comsat; situation + comedy = sitcom; users + network = UseNet; fan + magazine = fanzine; web + magazine = webzine; web + seminar = webinar; net + citizen = netizen; news + broadcast = newscast;* Uzbek mass media terms which are created by blending method contain not so many terms: *Jurnalistika + fakulteti = jurfak.*

As above mentioned, mass media terminology plays a significant role in existing new units of language. There are several ways of formation in creating new words in English and Uzbek mass media terminology. So, the ways of word formation - borrowing, compounding, morphological derivation and acronymy are productive in both English and Uzbek languages, however, blending is a productive way of word formation while, it is non-productive way of word formation in Uzbek mass media terminology.

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